

TABLE 1—MERCURIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES AND MERCAPTANS (THROUGH TRITHIOCARBONATE FORMATION)

Compounds	Values are mean of ten determinations with standard deviation ($\pm$)	
	Amount found*, mg	Amount found**, mg
<i>Organotrithiocarbonates (TTC)</i>		
$\begin{array}{c} \text{RS}-\text{C}-\text{SK} \\ \\ \text{S} \end{array}$		
Benzyl TTC (R, C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -)	5.05, 0.063	12.10, 0.080
Dodecyl TTC (R, C ₁₂ H ₂₅ -)	5.04, 0.048	11.90, 0.098
β -Ethanol TTC (R, OHCH ₂ CH ₂ -)	4.96, 0.081	12.09, 0.080
Isopropyl TTC [R, (CH ₃) ₂ CH-]	5.00, 0.052	12.07, 0.101
Isobutyl TTC [R, (CH ₃) ₂ CH-CH ₂ -]	4.95, 0.073	11.88, 0.089
* Amount taken, 5 mg ; **Amount taken, 12 mg		
<i>Mercaptans</i>		
Benzyl mercaptan	4.03, 0.056	10.00, 0.076
Dodecyl mercaptan	4.00, 0.052	10.08, 0.101
β -Mercaptoethanol	3.98, 0.048	9.92, 0.092
Isobutyl mercaptan	4.00, 0.058	10.10, 0.085
Isopropyl mercaptan	3.96, 0.079	9.98, 0.080
Thiophenol	4.03, 0.088	10.03, 0.102
2-Mercaptobenzothiazol	4.05, 0.088	9.91, 0.084
* Amount taken, 4 mg ; **Amount taken, 10 mg		

0.5 ml of carbon disulphide, 5-7 ml of potassium hydroxide (approx. 0.05 N) and 30 ml of water. The contents were shaken and the resulting yellow coloured solution (alkali salts of organotrithiocarbonic acids form yellow coloured solutions) was neutralised with very dilute solution of acetic acid using phenolphthalein as indicator. Diphenylcarbazine indicator (0.5 ml) was added to each solution which was titrated at room temperature (24°) with standard (0.0125 M) mercury(II) acetate solution to the appearance of blue colour. From the volume of titrant used corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each mercaptan was calculated. Results are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The methods involving mercury(II) reagents have quite extensively been used for the determination of organosulphur compounds. The present communication extends the use of such methods to organotrithiocarbonates. Since these compounds are conveniently prepared from mercaptans, it was considered highly desirable to investigate if the method could be extended so as to determine mercaptans after their conversion to trithiocarbonates. Mercaptan solutions turn yellow immediately on reacting with an excess of carbon disulphide in presence of an alkali, indicating the formation of organotrithiocarbonate (alkali organotrithiocarbonates form yellow solutions). The transformation of mercaptan to trithiocarbonate is immediate. The quantitative nature of this transformation has already been shown by Verma *et al.*^{3,7} and once again by the high accuracy

attained in the determination of mercaptans by this method. The excess of carbon disulphide does not interfere in the analysis of mercaptans. Both organotrithiocarbonates and mercaptans (after conversion to trithiocarbonates) have been successfully titrated with mercury(II) in aqueous medium in pH range 7.5-8.5 using diphenylcarbazine indicator to the appearance of blue colour. The overall standard deviations calculated from the pooled data of all the titrations performed with 5 and 12 mg of each trithiocarbonate have been found to be ± 0.063 and 0.090 , respectively (Table 1). The same for 4 and 10 mg of each mercaptan are ± 0.064 and 0.089 , respectively (Table 1).

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References

- E. E. REID, "Organic Chemistry of Bivalent Sulphur", Chemical Publishing Co., New York, 1962, Vol 4, p. 177.
- B. C. VERMA and S. KUMAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1015.
- B. C. VERMA and V. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1190.
- B. C. VERMA and S. KUMAR, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 612.
- B. C. VERMA and S. KUMAR, *Microchem. J.*, 1977, **22**, 149.
- B. C. VERMA and S. KUMAR, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1977, **32**, 2446.
- B. C. VERMA and S. KUMAR, *Microchem. J.*, 1978, **23**, 179.
- B. C. VERMA and S. KUMAR, *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1978, **4**, 61.
- G. GATTOW and W. BEHRENDT, "Topics in Sulphur Chemistry: Carbon sulphide and their Inorganic and Complex Chemistry", Georg Thieme Publishers, Stuttgart, 1977, Vol 2, p. 183.
- M. R. F. ASHWORTH, "The Determination of Sulphur Containing Groups", Academic Press, London, 1976, Vol 2, p. 65.
- J. H. KARCHMER, "The Analytical Chemistry of Sulphur and Its Compounds. Part I", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970, p. 492.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", The Elbs and Longmans, London, 1968.

Determination of Copper in Steel, Brass, Gunmetal, Nickel-Silver and Aluminium Alloy by Extraction with Phenanthraquinone Monothiosemicarbazone

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In this communication we propose a rapid and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of copper in ferrous and non-ferrous alloys using phenanthraquinone monothiosemicarbazone (PQMT) as the chromogenic reagent

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(synthesized by the reported method¹). The orange red coloured copper-PQMT complex extracted into chloroform from an acetate buffer solution of pH 5.5, absorbs at 540 nm and facilitates determination of copper in presence of a large number of cations.

Several solvent extraction methods for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of copper are known and a number of chelating agents²⁻²⁰ have been used for the purpose. However, these methods have some limitations, incomplete extraction^{2,3}, longer extraction period^{6-10,21}, a large number of interferences^{2,3,6,7,17,18} and use of either masking agent¹⁸ or synergetic extractant²⁰ may be cited as examples. The proposed method is free from these drawbacks. The method is comparable with neocuproin¹⁷ extraction method, but the proposed method is free from interference due to chromium and phosphate.

Procedure for extraction and determination of copper: Steel sample (500 mg) is dissolved in aqua regia, evaporated nearly to dryness and then diluted to 100 ml. Brass (1 g) or gunmetal is dissolved in 10 ml of conc. nitric acid, evaporated to dryness, extracted with 4 ml conc. sulphuric acid and diluted to 250 ml. Similarly, nickel-silver (1 g) is dissolved in nitric acid, evaporated, extracted with water and diluted to 250 ml. Aluminium alloy (1 g), however, is dissolved in aqua regia, evaporated to a small volume, 10 ml conc. hydrochloric acid is added and the solution diluted to the mark with water in 100 ml volumetric flask.

An aliquot of any of the above solutions, containing 2.5 to 35 µg of copper is taken and 2 ml of 0.06% (w/v) PQMT solution dissolved in DMF and 20 ml of acetate buffer, pH 5.5 (1.0 M) are added. The mixture is extracted for only 15 sec in a 100 ml separatory funnel with two 5 ml portions of chloroform. The organic phase is collected and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance of the orange-red complex is measured at 540 nm (Zeiss spectrophotometer; 1 cm silica cells) against a reagent blank prepared analogously. The results of triplicate analysis of standard samples and synthetic mixtures are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

The copper-PQMT complex (15 µg copper) extracted into chloroform from an acetate buffer solutions of pH 5.5 show λ_{max} at 540 nm whereas the reagent shows negligible absorbance at this wave length. The extraction of copper was studied at various pH (pH was adjusted with 1 M acetic acid and 1 M sodium hydroxide solution). The optimum extraction was between pH 4.8 and 5.5 and it decreased beyond this range (Table 3). The complex obeys Beer's law over the concentration range of 2.5 to 35 µg/10 ml of organic phase at 540 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex is 1.16×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.005 µg/cm² respectively. The colour of the complex is

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF COPPER IN STANDARD SAMPLES*

Sample	Composition	Copper content %		Relative error %
		Reported	Found	
93 d steel (NBS)	C 2.3, Si 1.63 Mn 0.63, Ni 2.38, Cr 0.32, Mn 0.48, Fe 90.3	1.54	1.52	1.3
41 brass (NML)	Pb 2.35, Zn 40.65, Fe 0.009	56.9	56.5	0.7
Gunmetal	Zn 4.4, Sn 5.3, Pb 6.3	83.1	84.0	1.07
Nickel-silver	Ni 18.2, Mn 0.27, Bi 0.6, Zn 25.8	55.1	54.7	0.6
Aluminium alloy	Ni 2.12, Mn 1.7, Fe 0.031 and rest Al	4.0	3.96	1.2

* Triplicate analysis.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN SYNTHETIC SAMPLES*

Sample No.	Composition of mixture µg	Copper recovered %	Relative error %
1	Cu 15, Mn 1500 Al 1000, Ni 1000	98.3	1.7
2	Cu 15, Fe 1500, Ni 500, Bi 100, Mo 100	98.7	1.3
3	Cu 15, Cr 100, V 100, Mn 100, Ni 100	99.0	1.0
4	Cu 15, Zn 1000, Pb 100, Fe 100	98.3	1.7

* Triplicate analysis.

TABLE 3—EXTRACTION OF COPPER(II)-PQMT BETWEEN CHCl₃ AND AQUEOUS SOLUTION AS A FUNCTION OF pH

pH	% Extraction	D, Distribution ratio
2	63.6	4.3
3	76.4	8.0
4	87.2	17.0
4.5	96.2	63.3
4.8-5.5	100.0	∞
5.8	85.0	14.2
6	73.6	6.9

stable for 24 hr. 2 ml of 0.06% reagent and 15 sec shaking time are enough for quantitative extraction of copper (2.5 to 35 µg).

The complex is soluble in solvents such as chloroform, MIBK, iso-amylalcohol and ethylacetate and extracts partially in benzene and toluene. Carbon tetrachloride is not suitable for extraction of the complex. For further studies chloroform was selected as it facilitates quick separation of the two phases.

Effect of foreign ions: Varying amounts of foreign ions were taken with fixed amount of copper (15 µg) and the recommended procedure was followed for extraction and absorbance measurements. Ag(I) (2 mg), Co(II) (300 µg), Zn(II) (2.5 mg), Cd(II) (1.5 mg), Mn(II) (1.5 mg), Sn(II)

(1 mg), Ni(II) (5 mg), Hg(II) (300 µg), Pb(II) (2.5 mg), Al(III) (3 mg), Bi(III) (1.5 mg), Cr(III) (100 µg), Au(III) (250 µg), Sb(III) (100 µg), Ru(III) (500 µg), Rh(III) (150 µg), Ir(III) (100 µg), Fe(III) (2 mg), La(III) (1 mg), Sn(IV) (100 µg), Pt(IV) (2.5 mg), Th(IV) (150 mg), Se(IV) (500 µg), V(V) (2 mg), U(VI) (1 mg), Cr(VI) (500 µg), Os(VI) (2.5 mg) and anions such as phosphate (150 µg), fluoride (1 mg), bromide (250 µg) and chloride (500 µg) do not interfere in the estimation of copper. Of the ions tested only palladium, tellurite, tartrate, citrate, ascorbate and EDTA showed interference.

The standard deviation of the mean absorbance for 15 µg of copper was found to be 0.006. The method has thus good precision.

Composition of the complex: The composition of the coloured complex was found to be 1:2 (metal to ligand ratio) by Job's continuous variation²² and the mole ratio method²³. The dissociation constant K, of the complex was evaluated by the expression

$$K = \frac{(m\alpha C)^m (n\alpha C)^n}{C(1-\alpha)}$$

where m and n are the number of metal ions and ligand molecules in complex, C is molar concentration and α is the degree of dissociation.

$$\alpha = \frac{A_m - A_s}{A_m}$$

where A_m and A_s are maximum absorbance (extrapolated value) and absorbance at stoichiometric molar ratio. The dissociation constant of the copper-PQMT complex was found to be 2.16×10^{-10} .

Conclusion: The proposed method for photometric determination of copper with phenanthraquinone monothiosemicarbazone is new, rapid and selective. The results are accurate and the wide applicability of the method has been demonstrated

by the satisfactory analysis of synthetic mixtures and standard samples.

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References

1. S. DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 7, 361.
2. A. H. I. BENBASSET and G. FRYDMAN-KUPFER *Chemist Analyst*, 1962, 51, 44.
3. J. STARY and E. HLADKY, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 28, 227.
4. T. SHIGEMATSU, M. TABUSHI and T. TARUMOTO, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1968, 84, 181.
5. W. S. SCRIBNER, W. J. TREAT, J. D. WEIS and R. W. MOSHEIR, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, 37, 1804.
6. W. G. SCRIBNER and A. M. KOTECKI, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, 37, 1804.
7. S. M. KHOPKAR and A. K. DE, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1959, 171, 241.
8. R. A. BOLOMEY and L. WISH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4883.
9. E. W. BERG and R. T. MCINTYRE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 27, 195.
10. A. HIDEO, H. KAWAMOTO and A. MASANOBU, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1971, 44, 117.
11. E. W. BERG and M. C. DAY, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 18, 578.
12. R. T. MCINTYRE, E. W. BERG and D. N. CAMPBELL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 1816.
13. J. N. SRIVASTAVA and R. P. SINGH, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc., Taipei*, 1974, 21, 275.
14. K. KESIUREA, *Chemia analit.*, 1967, 12, 401.
15. T. B. AMIRKHANOVA, V. S. PODGORNOVA and I. P. SHESTREOVA, *Zhur. Khim.* 19GD, 19G 55, 1967, *Anal. Abstract*, 1968, 15, 3174.
16. D. BRITTERIDGE, D. JOHN and F. SNAPP, *Analyst, Lond.*, 1973, 98, 512.
17. B. NEBSAR, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, 36, 1961.
18. N. V. BENEDIKTOVA-LODOCHIKOVA, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1963, 18, 1322.
19. M. V. R. MURTI and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Talanta*, 1978, 25, 165.
20. F. KAMIL, S. K. SINDHANWANI and R. P. SINGH, *Ann. Chim.*, 1978, 68, 71.
21. L. G. BORCHERDT and J. P. BUTLER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 29, 414.
22. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, 9, 133.
23. J. H. YOR, and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal.*, 1944, 16, 111.